

AN ASSESSMENT ON INSTRUCTIONAL METHODS USED BY THE SOCIAL SCIENCE TEACHERS AT MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY-SULU: STUDENTS' PERSPECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

This is a descriptive-correlational study which determines the extent of students' assessment of the instructional methods used by Social Science teachers at Mindanao State University (MSU)-Sulu during the Academic Year 2022 – 2023. Adopting weighted mean, standard deviation, t-Test for independent samples, One-way ANOVA, and Pearson's r test of correlation, this study reveals the following findings: 1) On demographic profile; out of 100 student-respondents, more than one-third is within 18 years old & above, mostly male, equally distributed in four year levels, whose parents have elementary level of education, and whose parents' average monthly income is within 5,000–10,000 range. 2) Generally, the used of instructional methods by social science teachers are preferred by college students across year levels. 3) Profile variables such as year level and parent's educational attainment intervened in ways how students assessed the extent of instructional methods used by social science teachers. 4) Teaching Methods and Learning Conditions are moderately correlated. 5) This study tends to confirm Gestalt Theory, which stresses that learning is a process of acquiring and integrating into one's personality, information, skills, habits and attitudes. Learning takes place when the whole being and the total stimulation are considered. This simply means that the individual does not only act merely to stimulus but rather to the background and setting. A teacher, through his/her instructional methods affects the students' initiatives and enthusiasm. Since instruction should begin at the point of interest of the student, a full knowledge of students preferred instructional methods is required.

Keywords: *Instructional Methods, Assessment, Social Science, Perspective, Teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is to be interpreted as a process of stimulating, directing and guiding the learner. The teacher must have an intensive knowledge and understanding of the physical, mental, social and emotional potentialities of those educational activities he hopes to direct and guide.

Teacher education today differs considerably from the past in which it consisted of a few courses on educational theory. Programs are much more field oriented than ever before, requiring prospective teachers to spend more time onsite working with students in school. The present emphasis on practical experience with students should not be interpreted as a movement away from theory. Rather, educational theory is being integrated with practice. This integration recognizes that theory, to be internalized, must be learned in the context in which it is being applied. Social Science is one of the fundamental learning areas wherein a person must greatly involve himself. It is empirical that every individual must equip himself with the necessary concepts and skills in Social Science. In everyday living, one uses Social Science, whether one is aware of it or not, (Bhatnagar, 2018).

Each school day, millions of parents entrust their most precious possessions to the care and influence of teachers. It should come as no surprise that what teachers do and how they do it are subjects of great interest and potentially intense controversy. Undeniably, a teacher is a person whose primary profession or occupational function is to help others learn and develop new ways because students are passive learners and that their minds are like blank slates to be filled up with bits of knowledge and information, (Prescot and David, 1976).

Apparently, teachers are now struggling with students who are difficult to teach, where no one version of teaching strategy is likely to be most effective with all of them. The wide number of variables on which these students differ interacts with the strategy's teachers use to teach them, (Wohlwill and Heft, 1987; Moore et al, 2003).

There is a need to build a repertoire of teaching strategies from which the teacher could select one that fits the learning situations. It is then the aim of this research to assess the effects of different instructional methods used by Social Science teachers as perceived by the students of Mindanao State University-Sulu.

Research Questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of student-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age,
 - 1.2 gender,
 - 1.3-year level,
 - 1.4 parent's educational attainment, and 1.5 parent's average monthly income?

2. What is the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers of MSU-Sulu as perceived by students in the context of:
 - 2.1 Teaching Methods; and
 - 2.2 Learning Conditions?
3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of:
 - 3.1 Age;
 - 3.2 Gender;
 - 3.3 Year Level;
 - 3.4 Parents Educational Attainment; and
 - 3.5 Parents Monthly Income?
4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu in terms of teaching methods, and learning conditions?

METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is a blueprint that guides the researcher from the very inception of the scientific investigation until its very completion (Harris, 1979).

Hence, this chapter centers its brief discussion on the following aspects: research design, research locale, respondents of the study, research instrument, sampling design, data gathering procedure, validity and reliability and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

Owing that there was a hypothesis validated in this study, the research design used is descriptive-exploratory in nature. It aimed to appraise the instructional methods used by Social Science Teachers as perceived by the students of Mindanao State University-Sulu.

This method was utilized because a descriptive method collates, tests and validates data. Description emerges following creative exploration, and serves to organize the findings in order to fit them with explanations, and then test or validate those explanations (Krathwohl, 1993). Furthermore, a descriptive research design interprets and reveals condition that exists or do not exist and explanatorily supplies the needed knowledge and experiences that will aid in setting a more detailed study, (Venson, 2004).

Research Locale

The study was conducted among the Students of Mindanao State University-Sulu, during the school year 2022-2023. Mindanao State University is located in the Municipality of Jolo, Province of Sulu. Jolo is the capital town of Sulu.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were one hundred (100) Students of Mindanao State University-Sulu during the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, respondents included in this study were students taking Social Science as major or subjects as part of their academic requirements in the aforesaid school. Twenty-five (25) students were drawn in each year level from 1st year to 4th year. Table below shows the distribution of samples in this study.

Table 1.1: Distribution of Samples by Year Level

Mindanao State University-Sulu	Number of Student-Respondents
First Year	25
Second Year	25
Third Year	25
Fourth Year	25
TOTAL	100

Sampling Design

A non-probability sampling method through purposive sampling procedure was employed in this study. That is, due to access, availability and time constraints, representative samples of twenty-five (25) students were drawn as representative for each year level, from First Year to Fourth Year. The use of purposive sampling procedure ensures the collection of desired quality and quantity of data used in this study.

Data Gathering Procedure

In the collection of data, a permit to administer the questionnaire was sought from the Dean of the School of Graduate Studies of Sulu State College and then from the University Chancellor, University Vice Chancellor for Academic Affairs and from the College Deans. The researcher conducted the launching and administration as well as the retrieval of the questionnaire personally.

After such, the questionnaire was subjected to presentation, analysis and interpretation of data. Then, a final draft was submitted for finalization and corrections.

Research Instrument

The study used a descriptive method of research. Questionnaire was the main instrument utilized in gathering the empirical data needed in this study. Interviews were also conducted to verify data collected.

The students' set of questionnaires is composed of three parts. Part I Respondent's Demographic Profile (Age, Gender, Year Level, Parent's Educational Attainment, Parent's Monthly Income, and Part II Extent of Instructional Methods used by the Social Science Teachers which is then categorized as: A – Teaching Methods, and B – Learning Condition

Validity and Reliability

Since this particular study utilized the standardized questionnaire of Tagle, R., (2007). This standardized instrument was already used in previous studies; thus, their validity and reliability are already established. Therefore, there is no need for the present researcher to undergo revalidation and retesting processes of the reliability of this instrument.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

In generating the primary empirical data for this study, the following statistical tools were employed;

- 1. Frequency and Percentage.** The frequency and percentage are the statistical tools used to determine the profile of the students as to gender, age, year level, parent's educational attainment, and parent's monthly income.
- 2. Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation.** The weighted mean and standard deviation were used to determine the extent of Instructional Methods Used by the Social Science teachers at Mindanao State University – Sulu in terms of Teaching Methods and Learning Conditions.
- 3. T-test and One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).** T-test for independent variable were employed to determine the significant differences in the extent of Instructional Methods Used by the Social Science teachers at Mindanao State University – Sulu when data are grouped according gender; and One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) will be employed to determine the significant differences in the extent of Instructional Methods Used by the Social Science teachers at Mindanao State University – Sulu when data are grouped according to age, year level, parent's educational attainment, and parent's monthly income.
- 4. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation.** Pearson product-moment correlation were used to determine the significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the Instructional Methods Used by the Social Science

teachers at Mindanao State University – Sulu in terms of Teaching Methods and Learning Conditions.

Table 1.2: SCALE TO BE USED

Point	Scale Value	Interpretation
5	4.50 – 5.00	Highly Preferred
4	3.50 – 4.49	Preferred
3	2.50 – 3.49	Moderately Preferred
2	1.50 – 2.49	Not Preferred
1	1.00 – 1.49	Highly Not Preferred

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section deals with the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results based on the data gathered for this study. Specifically, it illustrates the extent of students' assessment of the instructional methods used by Social Science teachers at Mindanao State University (MSU)-Sulu. It also deals with student-respondent's demographic profiles in terms age, gender, year level, parent's educational attainment, and Parent's average monthly income; the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers as perceived by students in the context of Teaching Methods and Learning Conditions; and the significant correlation and differences in these sub-categories when data are classified according to student-respondent's demographic profiles.

The following are the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results based on the proper scoring and statistical treatments of data gathered for this study that which correspond to each of the research questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of student-respondents in terms of: 1.1 age, 1.2 gender, 1.3-year level, 1.4 parent's educational attainment, and 1.5 parent's average monthly income?

1.1 In terms of Age

Table 1.1 reflects the demographic profile of student-respondents in terms of age. It can be browsed from this table that out of 100 student-respondents, 40 (40.0%) are 18 years old & below, 34 (34.0%) are 19-20 years old, 22 (22.0%) are 21-22 years old, and 4 (4.0%) are 23 years old & above. This result reveals that more than one-third of the total student-respondents involved in this study are within 18 years old & below. This result implies that students at MSU-Sulu involved in this study are within the lowest age bracket as categorized in this study.

Table 1.1 Demographic profile of student-respondents at MSU-Sulu in terms of age

Age	Number of Students	Percent
18 years old & below	40	40.0%
19-20 years old	34	34.0%
21-22 years old	22	22.0%
23 years old & above	4	4.0%
Total	100	100%

1.2 In terms of Gender

Table 1.2 shows the demographic profile of student-respondents in terms of gender. It can be gleaned from this table that out of 100 pupil-respondents, 56 (56.0%) are male, and 44 (44.0%) are female. This result reveals that more than one-half of the total student-respondents involved in this study are male. This result implies that students of MSU-Sulu who participated in this study, though with little disparity are more of male gender.

Table 1.2 Demographic profile of student-respondents at MSU-Sulu in terms of gender

Gender	Number of Students	Percent
Male	56	56.0%
Female	44	44.0%
Total	100	100%

1.3 In terms of Year Level

Table 1.3 shows the demographic profile of student-respondents in terms of year level. It can be gleaned from this table that out of 100 student-respondents, 25 (25.0%) are first year, 24 (24.0%) are second year, 26 (26.0%) is third year, and 25 (25.0%) are fourth year. This result reveals that student-respondents involved in this study are almost equally prorated into the four-year levels.

Table 1.3 Demographic profile of student-respondents at MSU-Sulu in terms of year level

Year Level	Number of Students	Percent
First Year	25	25.0%
Second Year	24	24.0%
Third Year	26	26.0%
Fourth Year	25	25.0%
Total	100	100%

1.4 In terms of Parent's Educational Attainment

Table 1.4 presents the demographic profile of student-respondents in terms of parent's educational attainment. It can be gleaned from this table that out of 100 student-respondents, 38 (38.0%) are whose parents have no formal education, 50 (50.0%) are whose parents have elementary level of education, 8 (8.0%) are whose parents have secondary level of education, and 4 (4.0%) are whose parents have college level of education. This result indicates that one-half of the total student-respondents are whose parents have elementary level of education. It implies that student-respondents who participated in this study could hardly obtain academic supports from their parents given that most of their parents have merely elementary level of education.

Table 1.4 Demographic profile of student-respondents at MSU-Sulu in terms of parent's educational attainment

Parent's Educational Attainment	Number of Students	Percent
No formal education	38	38.0%
Elementary level	50	50.0%
Secondary level	8	8.0%
College level	4	4.0%
Total	100	100%

1.5 In terms of Parent's Average Monthly Income

Table 1.5 shows the demographic profile of student-respondents in terms of parent's average monthly income. This table reveals that out of 100 student-respondents, 67 (67.0%) are whose parents with 5,000 & below, 27 (27.0%) are whose parents with 5,000 – 10,000, 4 (04.0%) are whose parents with 10,000 – 15,000, and 2 (2.0%) are whose parents with 15,000 & above of average monthly family income, respectively. This result reveals that great majority of the parents of the student-respondents are whose parents' average monthly income is within 5,000 – 10,000 range. This result implies that, most of the students at MSU-Sulu are whose parents considered as low-income earners; hence, these students could hardly obtain sufficient financial support from their parents for their schooling.

Table 1.5 Demographic profile of student-respondents at MSU-Sulu in terms of parent's average monthly income

Parent's Average Monthly Income	Number of Students	Percent
5,000 & below	67	67.0%
5,000 – 10,000	27	27.0%

10,000 – 15,000	4	4.0%
15,000 & above	2	2.0%
Total	100	100%

2. What is the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers of MSU-Sulu as perceived by students in the context of: 2.1 Teaching Methods; and 2.2 Learning Conditions?

2.1 In terms of Teaching Methods

Table 2.1 shows the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers of MSU-Sulu as perceived by students in the context of teaching methods. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.3233 with standard deviation of .24266 which is rated as “Preferred”. This result indicates that students at MSU-Sulu preferred the art of teaching used by teachers the one with the use of devices and application of methods and principles in teaching in order to affect the proper development of the individual student. It implies that college instructors are employing instructional method in teaching social science that requires the use of varied teaching devices.

It is noticeable that student-respondents rated the following items as “Preferred”: “Lecture-it is a teaching procedure for clarifying or explaining a major idea cast in the form of question or a problem. This type can be dominated by the teacher, can be discussion between the class and the teacher, and can be accompanied by visual materials such as slides, films and transparencies”, “Laboratory/experimental-one way of teaching that actively involves every student in the class in manipulating materials and simple equipment to find answers to questions and solve problems”, “Problem solving-refers to the process of removing difficulty through rational procedures involving analytical and reflective thinking”, “Fieldtrip-it is an out of classroom activity whereby students study things in their natural settings”, and “Reading/study type- this methodology requires students to gather facts and information or solve problems by reading printed materials”. Table 2.1 Extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers of MSU-Sulu as perceived by students in the context of teaching methods

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Demonstration-this learning activity is performed by a student or a teacher while the rest of the class observe. This activity is done for experiments involving expensive materials or due to lack of materials.	4.790 0	.43333	Highly Preferred
2	Lecture-it is a teaching procedure for clarifying or explaining a major idea	4.270 0	.46829	Preferred

	cast in the form of question or a problem. This type can be dominated by the teacher, can be discussion between the class and the teacher, and can be accompanied by visual materials such as slides, films and transparencies.			
3	Project-is a significant unit of problematic nature, planned and carried to completion by the learners in the natural manner and involving the use of physical materials to complete the unit of experience.	4.610 0	.54855	Highly Preferred
4	Laboratory/experimental-one way of teaching that actively involves every student in the class in manipulating materials and simple equipment to find answers to questions and solve problems.	4.390 0	.60126	Preferred
5	Problem solving-Refers to the process of removing difficulty through rational procedures involving analytical and reflective thinking.	4.210 0	.62434	Preferred
6	Fieldtrip-it is an out of classroom activity whereby students study things in their natural settings.	3.980 0	.75183	Preferred
7	Reading/study type- this methodology requires students to gather facts and information or solve problems by reading printed materials.	4.200 0	.65134	Preferred
8	Games-These are activities or contests governed by sets of rules. People engage in games for recreation and to develop mental or physical skills.	4.140 0	.73882	Preferred
9	Debate-this methodology requires one to talk or argue about something at length and in detail, especially as part of a formal exchange of opinion.	4.320 0	.70896	Preferred
Total Weighted Mean		4.323 3	.24266	Preferred

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Highly Preferred; (4) 3.50-4.49= Preferred; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Moderately Preferred; (2) 1.50- 2.49= Not Preferred; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Highly Not Preferred

2.2 In terms of Learning Conditions

Table 2.2 shows the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers of MSU-Sulu as perceived by students in the context of learning conditions. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.2142 with standard deviation of .25984 which is rated as “Preferred”. This result indicates that students at MSU-Sulu preferred the kind of learning conditions they presently have as effective instructional methods in teaching social science. It implies that college instructors are providing efficient learning conditions for students to learn effectively social science concepts.

It is noticeable that student-respondents rated the following items as “Preferred”: “Complexity of the subject matter”, “Availability of textbooks”, “Inadequacy of the library facilities”, “Inadequacy of audio-visual room, equipment and facilities”, “Limited school site”, “Poor classroom conditions”, “Inadequacy of children’s tables, chairs, lockers”, “Lack of manipulative materials”, and “Lack of learning resource centers/corners”.

Table 2.2 Extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers of MSU-Sulu as perceived by students in the context of learning conditions

Statements		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Knowledge of the teacher	4.7300	.46829	Highly Preferred
2	Complexity of the subject matter	4.2800	.53333	Preferred
3	Availability of textbooks	4.1600	.69224	Preferred
4	Inadequacy of the library facilities	4.1300	.64597	Preferred
5	Inadequacy of audio-visual room, equipment and facilities	4.1100	.68009	Preferred
6	Limited school site	4.0700	.71428	Preferred
7	Poor classroom conditions	3.9500	.65713	Preferred
8	Inadequacy of children’s tables, chairs, lockers	4.2500	.70173	Preferred
9	Lack of manipulative materials	4.2000	.66667	Preferred
10	Lack of learning resource centers/corners	4.2000	.69631	Preferred
11	Inappropriate attitudes of the students	4.1800	.62571	Preferred
12	Lack of administrative support	4.3100	.64659	Preferred
Total Weighted Mean		4.2142	.25984	Preferred

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Highly Preferred; (4) 3.50-4.49= Preferred; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Moderately Preferred; (2) 1.50- 2.49= Not Preferred; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Highly Not Preferred

3. Is there a significant difference in the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of: 3.1 Age; 3.2 Gender; 3.3 Year Level; 3.4 Parents Educational Attainment; and 3.5 Parents Monthly Income?

3.1 – According to Age

Table 3.1 presents the difference in the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age. It can be gleaned from this table that unlike “Teaching Methods” other sub-category such as “Learning Conditions” which subsumed under the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers with its corresponding F-value and probability value is indeed significant at alpha .05. This means that, student-respondents in this study despite that they vary in their age range, yet they indeed differ in their ways of assessing extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers. This result implies that a student-respondent being 23 years old & above may not probably make him/her better perceiver toward the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers as against those belong to 17-18 years old, 19-20 years old, 21-22 years old, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable age has no significant intervention in ways how student-respondents perceive towards the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by social science teachers. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age” is accepted.

Table 3.1 Difference in the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Teaching Methods	Between	.184	3	.061	1.043	.377	Not Significant
	Within Groups	5.646	96	.059			
	Total	5.830	99				
Learning Conditions	Between	1.277	3	.426	7.556	.000	Significant
	Within Groups	5.407	96	.056			
	Total	6.684	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

3.2 According to Gender

Table 3.2 presents the difference in the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender. It can be gleaned from this table that both sub-categories which subsumed under students' assessment of the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods with their corresponding Mean Differences, t-values and probability values are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, male and female student-respondents in this study although diverge in their gender; however, they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by social science teachers. This result implies that being a male student-respondent may not probably make him better perceiver toward the extent of effectiveness of instructional method used by teachers as against his female counterpart, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable gender has no significant intervention in ways how student-respondents perceive towards the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by social science teachers. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender" is accepted.

Table 3.2 Difference in the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender

VARIABLES				Mean			
Grouping		Mean	S. D.	Differenc	t	Sig.	Description
Teaching Methods	Male	4.3333	.19876	.02273	.463	.644	Not Significant
	Female	4.3106	.29111				
Learning Conditions	Male	4.2574	.23904	.09835	1.904	.060	Not Significant
	Female	4.1591	.27715				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

3.3 – According to Year Level

Table 3.3 presents the difference in the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of year level. It can be

gleaned from this table that the sub-category “Teaching Methods” which subsumed under students’ assessment of the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by teachers with its corresponding F-value and probability value is indeed significant at alpha .05. This means that, student-respondents in this study although vary in their year level; yet, they indeed differ in their assessment toward the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by social science teachers in terms of teaching methods. This result implies that a student-respondent being a fourth-year level may probably make him/her better perceiver toward the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by teachers in terms of teaching methods as against those enrolled in first year, second year, and third year levels, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable year level has indeed significant influence in the ways how student-respondents perceive towards the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods use by social science teachers in terms of teaching methods. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that “There is no significant difference in the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of year level” is rejected.

Table 3.3 Difference in the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of year level

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Teaching Methods	Between	.796	3	.265	5.062	.003	Significant
	Within Groups	5.033	96	.052			
	Total	5.830	99				
Learning Conditions	Between	.364	3	.121	1.843	.145	Not Significant
	Within Groups	6.320	96	.066			
	Total	6.684	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

A Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey Test was conducted to determine which among groups classified according to year level to have different levels of mean in area Teaching Methods when data are grouped according to student-respondents’ demographic profile in terms of year level.

The result of the analysis which is shown in Table 3.3.1 indicates that the difference in the means of the Teaching Methods is obtained by way of lower group means minus higher group means.

On Teaching Methods: It shows that Fourth Year group of student-respondents obtained the mean difference of $-.21778^*$ with Standard Error of $.06476$ and p-value of $.006$ which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over First Year students. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of student-respondents supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by social science teachers in terms of teaching methods than those students enrolled as Fourth Year College.

Table 3.3.1 Post Hoc Analysis: Differences in the level of mean in sub-category Teaching Methods when data are grouped according to year level

Dependent Variables	(I) Grouping by Age	(J) Grouping by Age	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
<i>Teaching Methods</i>	First Year	Second Year	-.14833	.06544	.113
		Third Year	-.02547	.06414	.979
		Fourth Year	-.21778*	.06476	.006

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

3.4 According to Parent's Educational Attainment

Table 3.4 presents the difference in the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of parent's educational attainment. It can be gleaned from this table that both of the sub-categories subsumed under students' assessment of the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods with their corresponding F-values and probability values are indeed significant at $\alpha .05$. This means that, student-respondents in this study despite that they vary in their parent's educational attainment; yet, they indeed differ in their assessment toward the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods. This result implies that a student-respondent being his/her parents are college graduates may probably make him/her better perceiver toward the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by social science teachers as against those whose parents have no formal education, have elementary and high school levels of education, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable parent's educational attainment has indeed significant intervention in ways how student-respondents perceive towards the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by social science teachers. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of parent's educational attainment" is rejected.

Table 3.4 Difference in the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of parent's educational attainment

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Teaching Methods	Between Groups	.538	3	.179	3.250*	.025	Significant
	Within Groups	5.292	96	.055			
	Total	5.830	99				
Learning Conditions	Between Groups	1.057	3	.352	6.008*	.001	Significant
	Within Groups	5.628	96	.059			
	Total	6.684	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

A Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey Test was conducted to determine which among groups classified according to parent's educational attainment to have different levels of mean in area Teaching Methods and Learning Conditions when data are grouped according to student-respondents' demographic profile in terms of parent's educational attainment.

The result of the analysis which is shown in Table 3.4.1 indicates that the difference in the means of the Teaching Methods and Learning Conditions are obtained by way of lower group means minus higher group means.

On Teaching Methods: It shows that student-respondent's parents with College Level group obtained the mean difference of $-.37281^*$ with Standard Error of $.12342$ and p-value of $.017$ which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over No Formal Education. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of student-respondents supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by social science teachers in terms of teaching methods than those students whose parents with College Level of education.

On Learning Conditions: It shows that student-respondent's parents with College Level group obtained the mean difference of $-.51974^*$ with Standard Error of $.12727$ and p-value of $.001$ which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over No Formal Education. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of student-respondents supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by social science teachers in terms of learning conditions than those students whose parents with College Level of education.

Table 3.4.1 Post Hoc Analysis: Differences in the level of mean in sub-categories Teaching Methods and Learning Conditions when data are grouped according to parent's educational attainment

Dependent Variables	(I) Grouping by Parent's Educational Attainment	(J) Grouping by Parent's Educational Attainment	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Teaching Methods	No Formal Education	Elementary	-.07392	.05053	.464
		Secondary	-.06725	.09133	.882
		College	-.37281*	.12342	.017
Teaching Methods	No Formal Education	Elementary	.00193	.05211	1.000
		Secondary	-.07182	.09418	.871
		College	-.51974*	.12727	.001

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

3.5 According to Parent's Average Monthly Income

Table 3.5 presents the difference in the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of parent's average monthly income. It can be gleaned from this table that both of the sub-categories subsumed under students' assessment of the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by social science teachers with their corresponding F-values and probability values are not significant at alpha .05. This means that, student-respondents in this study although vary in their parents' monthly income, still they do not differ in their perceptions toward the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by social science teachers. This result implies that a student-respondent whose parents are earning at 16,000 & above may not probably make him/her better perceiver toward the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods than those students whose parents are earning monthly income at 5,000 & below, 6,000 to 10,000; and 10,000 to 15,000, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable parent's average monthly income has no significant influence in the ways how student-respondents perceive towards the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by social science teachers. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of parent's average monthly income" is accepted.

Table 3.5 Difference in the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of parent's average monthly income

SOURCES OF VARIATION		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Description
Teaching Methods	Between	.347	3	.116	2.028	.115	Not Significant
	Within Groups	5.482	96	.057			
	Total	5.830	99				
Learning Conditions	Between	.262	3	.087	1.304	.278	Not Significant
	Within Groups	6.422	96	.067			
	Total	6.684	99				

*Significant at alpha 0.05

4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu in terms of teaching methods, and learning conditions?

Table 4 illustrates the correlation between the sub-categories subsumed under extent of the effectiveness of instructional methods used by the social science teachers at Mindanao State University - Sulu in terms of teaching methods, and learning conditions. It can be gleaned from this table that the computed Pearson Correlation Coefficients (Pearson's r) between these variables is significant at alpha .05.

Specifically, the degree of correlation between the sub-categories of subsumed under the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by social science teachers in the context of Teaching Methods and Learning Conditions is as follows:

- 1) Moderate positive correlation between Teaching Methods AND Learning Conditions.

This result indicates that the group student-respondents who generally perceived the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by social science teachers at Mindanao State University-Sulu in the context of Teaching Methods as "Preferred" are possibly the same group of student-respondents who perceived Learning Conditions as "Preferred" respectively.

Meanwhile, it is safe to say that, generally the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods used by social science teachers at Mindanao State University-Sulu in the context of Teaching Methods and Learning Conditions is moderately correlated.

Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, "There is no significant correlation between the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of effectiveness of instructional

methods at Mindanao State University-Sulu in the context of Teaching Methods and Learning Conditions” is rejected.

Table 4. Correlation between the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of effectiveness of instructional methods at Mindanao State University (MSU) – Sulu in the context of Teaching Methods and Learning Conditions

Variables		Pearson <i>r</i>	Sig	N	Description
Dependent	Independent				
Teaching Methods	Learning Conditions	.414**	.000	100	Moderate

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at alpha .05

Correlation Coefficient Scales Adopted from Hopkins, Will (2002):

0.0-0.1=Nearly Zero; 0.1-0.30=Low; .3-0.5 0=Moderate; .5-0.7-0=High; .7-0.9= Very High; 0.9-1=Nearly Perfect

Conclusions

This study concludes the following:

- 1) In this study, students of Mindanao State University–Sulu are sufficiently represented in terms of age, gender, year level, parent’s educational attainment, and parent’s average monthly income.
- 2) Generally, the used of instructional methods by social science teachers are preferred by college students across year levels.
- 3) Profile variables such as year level and parent’s educational attainment intervened in ways how students assessed the extent of instructional methods used by social science teachers.
- 4) Teaching Methods and Learning Conditions are moderately correlated.
- 5) This study tends to confirm Gestalt Theory, which stresses that learning is a process of acquiring and integrating into one’s personality, information, skills, habits and attitudes. Learning takes place when the whole being and the total stimulation are considered. This simply means that the individual does not only act merely to stimulus but rather to the background and setting. A teacher, through his/her instructional methods affects the students’ initiatives and enthusiasm. Since instruction should begin at the point of interest of the student, a full knowledge of students preferred instructional methods is required.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following:

- 1) Administrator/s of Mindanao State University-Sulu should continue to sustain the provision of efficient learning conditions by providing sufficient in-service training programs for social science teachers.
- 2) Social Science instructors should be provided with more professional trainings that would enhance their pedagogical knowledge and skills in the use of effective instructional methods.
- 3) More instructors should be encouraged to pursue graduate studies specifically in the field of social science teaching.
- 4) Moreover, student-researchers in the field of social science teaching are encouraged to conduct study similar to this one but to include other variables such as social science learning strategies, academic achievement, and social science learning anxiety in some other settings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher asked the panels of expert to validate the questionnaires first. Then, the researcher asked the permission from the office of the Dean of the Graduate School, Sulu State College, The Mindanao State University-Sulu Chancellor to launch the checklist questionnaires. As soon as the permission was granted, the researcher coordinated the College Dean and launched the questionnaires to the students as respondents. In like manner, the written consent form for both the school heads and students include the statement of confidentiality of data and privacy of the participants. In data gathering, the respondents were given a time to answer the questionnaires and the researcher retrieved the said questionnaires after duly accomplished by the students as respondents. As soon as the questionnaires were collected, the researcher tallied the responses on the SPSS program and further was computed to answer the research questions. I hereby certify that this research work is my own work and to the best of my knowledge, it contains no materials previously published by another person. I also certify that this work does not contain materials which, to a considerable extent, has been accepted in return for an academic degree of Master of Arts in Social Science. I further declare that the content of this research is the product of my own work. Any involvement made in this work by others or elsewhere is clearly acknowledge in the manuscript.

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